

**THE POLITICS OF HYDROHEGEMONY AND WATER
WEAPONIZATION: CONTEXTUALIZING THE ISRAEL-
PALESTINE CONFLICT IN A CONTESTED WEST ASIA**

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Abstract:

Resource Wars have become an inescapable reality in the 21st century. The Post-Cold War era has thrown light on the non-traditional security issues where resource scarcity across geographically challenged nations became focal points around which future wars could be waged. Among the natural resources, the centrality of water as a life saving commodity in the planet is a ubiquitous fact. Water politics as a parallel trajectory alongside mainstream hard politics has come to trigger off, if not dominate the contours of inter-state and regional diplomacy. In this context, West Asia emerges as the perfect example of such a flashpoint due to its water- stressed topography and increasing quest for water availability. The age-old Israel- Palestine conflict dating back to the past century was enormously dominated by the access to water resources despite overt religious and political connotations of such a conflict. In other words, Israel's hydrohegemony provoked the protracted conflict across decades and is still now in action. Using water as a bargaining chip for power centralization has not only augmented Israel- Palestine standoff but has also spilled over seeds of resource diplomacy across the conflict prone West Asian nations. This paper tends to analyze how Israel's hydrohegemony and weaponization of water has further fuelled its conflict with Palestine and what regional repercussion could a future hydrohegemony bring about in an already war splintered West Asia.

Keyword: West Asia, hydrohegemony, water, Israel, Palestine

Introduction

“Whiskey is for drinking and water is for fighting.”

- Mark Twain

(Innocents' Abroad, 1869, as cited in Bard, 2001, pg 30)

Nothing can truly bring out the essence of today's hydro politics than the words summed up by the famous American writer and humorist of the 19th century- Mark Twain. The current Israel- Palestine conflict can bear testimony to this statement in its entirety. Water scarcity has always been a grave reality in West Asia. Israel, like most of its neighbors in the region, harbors an arid climate with limited fresh water reserves. The paltry fresh water resources in the area had made the ancient people of the territory to regard water as a priceless diamond and liquid gold across the region. This was however before the advent of petroleum as the liquid gold and a major resource of geopolitics across the region. History has been replete with accounts of the leaders of the Abrahamic faiths hinting at the efficacy of freshwater and the necessity to preserve and use it wisely. Before the formation of the state of Israel, the Ottoman ruled Palestine had an organized water supply system. Though the availability of water was in itself scanty, it was still regulated and rationed according to the Sharia laws (Ward et al., 2021). Water during that time was upheld as a public property and allocated in terms of quotas of people who owned irrigated lands. Besides this, rain water was harvested in traditional cisterns or in the local springs during the rainy season. The hydrological topography of the Ottoman ruled Palestine hint at the presence of water in selected areas of the state. In the West Bank, the primary source of freshwater emanates from the Lake Tiberius which joins the upper bank of the Jordan River. It eventually drains into the lower bank of the Jordan River and joins the Dead Sea (Anderson, 2019). Due to the high salinity in the Dead Sea, the water along the lower banks of the Jordan River is usually not fit for human consumption. In the central area of the West Bank, freshwater reserves can be found across the Mountain Aquifers which is in turn divided into three areas- Northeastern Aquifers, Western Aquifers and the Eastern Aquifers (Ward et al., 2021). Almost 80% of the area's water demands are met by these aquifers which are primarily fed by rainwater (Stork, 1983). In the Gaza strip and in current day Israel, the Coastal Aquifers form the bastion of freshwater reserves mainly from direct rainfall and other sources like downpour from wells, reservoirs, tanks etc. Thus it can be seen that the main areas of freshwater reserves are located in either the West Bank or along the Gaza strip- both located in the current day Palestinian territory. With the formation of the state of the Jewish state of Israel in 1948, things took a different turn. The wealthy Jews

along with their economic potential developed hydropower and modern water supply systems across the Palestinian territories, especially in the West Bank and in the Gaza strip. Infact, all the traditional Palestinian water systems and water based territories were under the Jewish entrepreneurship thereby augmenting Jewish hold over the key water resources and shoving Palestine into the periphery (Ward et al., 2021). This in a way kick started the hydrohegemony of Israel over Palestine. As the Israeli economist Ariel Diner mentioned in 2003, “the issue of water ...is an issue intertwined in asymmetries, power relationships, history and ideological beliefs. Not only the early Zionists view water ideologically, but they were also able to demonstrate their power over the Arab inhabitants...the Zionists viewed the water and the necessity to control it and the reluctance to share it...a kind of psychological scarcity, a scarcity of resource in the eye of the beholder” (Zeitoun, 2009, 65).

Backdrop

Israel’s major masterstroke on hydrohegemony came in the year 1967 when it gained preponderance of water resources over Palestine with the occupation of the West Bank along the Jordan Basin and the Mountain Aquifers beyond the West Bank’s territory. In other words, the Jews took control over the central water reserve of the Palestinians which is the Mountain Aquifers (Stork, 1983). This was done at the expense of the Palestinians. Israel in its quest for water security had captured the West Bank territory and pushed the Palestinians out of their area thereby compelling them to settle in the fringes like refugees. The reason for this is very obvious- Israel from its outset was determined to achieve a full fledged statehood with a well laid out nation security policy. Security formed the main cornerstone of the newly formed Jewish state of Israel as the Jews were already the victims of holocaust and purges in the erstwhile Nazi Germany. The Jewish community was desperately in need of a secured territory with self sufficient resources to enable them to live respectfully and gain legitimacy as a distinct nation in the world. The Jewish faith necessitated them to believe that their cherished homeland will be in the territory between the Mediterranean and the Jordan River. Having rationalized their faith into reality, the Jews were determined to protect their novel state from any existential threat or crisis which could demean and obliterate their existence. To live a

decent life and prosper as a respectable nation, Israel must incorporate a modern industry, sound agricultural system and a self sufficient resource base (based on the availability of resources there). In the geographically and hydrologically parched territory, establishing control over finite resources was the key to secure stability in the long run. Water was a significant bargaining resource which acted as a trump card in Israel's fight over Palestine. With the Judaization of the so called Promised Land between the Jordan and the Mediterranean, efforts to bring them under agriculture were indispensable. Water would be needed to harvest as well as to build up solid industries for national and economic development. The Jewish immigrants gradually brought with them new industrial blueprints and indirectly insinuated a robust message to the international community for acceptance of the legitimate state of Israel. West Bank's water resources form almost 90% of Israel's water consumption needs. The water reservoirs in the West Bank include the local cisterns, wells, tanks etc. Before the Israeli occupation, the Palestinians in the West Bank territory did not know how to exploit the water resources to their advantages properly. After the occupation, the Israeli side was prompt enough to divert all the channels of water across the West Bank to hydrate the agricultural fields of the Jews. This was possible only as the Palestinian agriculture was not so developed and they lacked the proper skills to channelize the water to their ends. It was certain in the words of one Israeli writer when he said that, "our good luck is that the agriculture in the West Bank is not so developed" (Stork, 1983, 21). So it was easier for the Jews to grab the opportunity and sideline the Palestinians from any further encroachment in the area. Israel issued the famous 1967 military order by which it was stated that Israel had gained control over the territories of West Bank and Gaza strip for administrative and security concerns and also prohibited the Palestinians from opting any methods to extract fresh water. The Israeli side started drilling initiatives to pump out water from the wells for their fields and at the same time prevented the city of Ramallah to adopt any drilling permits. It was instead ordered to merge with the Israeli national system which was an integrated national water grid adopted by Israel whereby water from the northeastern aquifers will be circulated down in to the centre, west and eastern part of the whole Israeli territory. Reports from both the 1980s and the current era suggest that Israel has deliberately obstructed Palestinians from having access to water supplies

in the West Bank. During the 1980s Israel officially had only 7 drilled wells in the West Bank, albeit unofficial sources hinted at 27 of them (Stork, 1983). These wells alone drew more than 14 million cubic meters of water which was almost 40% higher than 33 million cubic meters drawn by only 314 Palestinian wells. However Israel in the present scenario has smoothly beaten its Palestinian counterpart in water consumption. A report from the Amnesty International has stated that by average a Palestinian citizen consumes only 73 liters of water per day which is well below the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended level of 100 liters per person per day (“ The Occupation of Water “, 2017). Also, according to the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), the water intake is as low as 20 liters per person per day along the Palestinian ghettos. Compared to that, Israel’s water consumption stands at 300 liters of water on an average (“The Occupation of Water”, 2017). On top of that, Israel has by now centralized the entire water infrastructure in the West Bank under its control. The Israeli state owned Water Company called Mekorot has submerged all Palestinian wells and devised strategies to pump water only to the Israeli inhabitants residing in the West Bank. The entire water used by Israel in the West Bank adds up to its agricultural and industrial development. The Israeli population in the West Bank receives satisfactory volumes of potable water for drinking, sanitization as well as for agricultural and industrial development. However the situation turned upside down in case of the Palestinians. Though a limited volume of water is occasionally sold to the Palestinians, but even that volume is subjected to official scrutiny by the Israeli authorities. Often, the Palestinians are compelled to pay exorbitant rates for few liters of water for their daily chores. Such a policy clearly hints at the weaponization of water by Israel along the West Bank to intimidate and subterfuge the Palestinians in their claim for an anti-Semitic Arabian homeland. The hydro hegemony of Israel also takes into account the access to the vital ports along the West Bank. The King Hussein Bridge- a major port in the West Bank and a bridge between Israel and Jordan is totally occupied by the Israelis and the Palestinians have no access to the strategic ports or chokepoints thereby cutting them off from the global trade market and the global supply chain networks. In Gaza too, we find the hegemony over water and its weaponization as a state sponsored and deliberate attempt by Israel to

counter the Palestinians and to win the access to strategic strongholds through the Egyptian territory, the Suez and finally into the Mediterranean (The Question of Palestine, United Nations). In the Gaza strip, the Coastal Aquifers forms the dominant mode of freshwater supplies and during the 20th century the Israelis had extracted more than 90% of the water from this area. In the current scenario, due to climate change related issues, rainfall is scanty in the Gaza strip and the western coast of Israel making the Coastal Aquifers contaminated and filled with saline water from the Mediterranean. In such a situation, Israel has halted its drainage of water from the Coastal Aquifers and instead prevented the supply of freshwater from the West Bank to the Gaza strip for the Palestinians. The Coastal Aquifers remains the only source of freshwater for the hapless Palestinians. Knowing the potential dangers of consumption of unfiltered and saline water, Israel has turned its back from the Gaza strip and subjected the Palestinian population with no choice other than to make use of such unhealthy water intake. Thus in relation to a full-scaled war, using water as a weapon and slowly poisoning the population in Palestine has crystallized Israel's hydro hegemony and its ulterior motive for a legitimate state of Israel free from any hue of Palestinian shadows. Securing enough water for its own population adds up to a country's national security policy. Israel has followed this strategy to completely refute the idea of a two state solution and bolster a brimming and booming Israel over a staggering and abating Palestinian demography thereby hinting at the possible takeover of the entire territory as the politically independent and legitimate state of Israel. Even the much hyped Oslo Accords of the 1990s proved to be a sham when looked at from the angle of hydro-politics. In the water sharing agreement of the Oslo Accords, the vital areas of the West Bank (almost 60%), Jordan River and the Gaza strip were excluded from the terms of the agreement. Israel did agree to supply water to the Palestinians according to its own interests and good will to which the latter agreed meekly (Black, 2013). The Palestinians succumbed to the Jewish colonization policies and subsequent hydrohegemony over them. The pricing of water to the Palestinians remained high due to which a number of illegal well constructions were carried out by them around their territory. This however irked the Israeli authorities and they unleashed incorrigible destruction to those constructions thereby spiking the hydrohegemony dominating Israeli perceptions.

Cause of Hydrohegemony and Lingering of the Current Conflict

The current Israel –Palestine conflict among many other factors points out at the command of water as a central factor for its protracted and elongated stature. In the present century, the Palestinian population is increasing rapidly. In 2024 itself, the population of Palestine stands at 5.43 million in contrast to 5.37 million in 2023 (Digital 2024, Palestine). This clearly indicates that there was a 2.3% increase in its population by one year. In 2022, it stood at 5.04 million which shows that in each year the population is leaping forward comfortably. As against this, the population of Israel stood at 9.24 million in 2024, but it grew only by 1.5% from its previous year highlighting at a declining rate (Digital 2024, Israel). For a territory to assume a proper statehood, one of the key defining factors is the demography of the territory. For Palestine, their hope for an Arab land can gain traction only with its increased demography. Also, more population demands more pressure on resources and more quests for access to water. Israel is not new to such comprehensions. Therefore in a bid to defy any Palestinian claims of statehood, Israel uses water as a weapon to curb the Palestinian flowering population. Israel currently controls more than 85% of the water reserves in both the West Bank and the Gaza strip and constantly focuses on targeting Palestinian settlements so that they lack access to fresh water. Squeezing out drops of water from the Palestinian strongholds also points out at a defiant Israel adept at making water a dangerous weapon to eliminate its enemy (McKernan, 2023). The Jewish preference for the West Bank and the Gaza hints at the aggressive strategy to encircle the Palestinians and weaponize water as a tool to wipe out their existence. Israel plays the typical hydro hegemon to augment its national interest and dislodge its dreaded enemy from rising into action as a powerful nation alongside its own image.

A second cause of such hydrohegemony can be traced back to the religious roots of the both communities. Infact religion forms the cornerstone of the Israel-Palestine conflict in the first place. It is religion which has made the entire Israel-Palestine saga to emerge and exist. For the Jews, the biblical reference to the reclamation of the holy land of Jerusalem is rooted in the hope of a water available land suitable for habitation. The Isaiah 44:3 reference mentions about Divine plans of hydrating the parched territory and residing in the Promised Land of the Jews. It says, “For I will pour water on the thirsty land, and streams on

the dry ground; I will pour my spirit upon your offspring, and my blessing on your descendants” (Book of Isaiah Old Testament, 2024). This line from the Book of Isaiah which is a vital component of the Old Testament reveals the Divine guidance for the Promised Land in an initially water deficient territory and later hoping to fill such a dry land with swirls of water from underneath the ground with the help of Divine intervention. The line also mentions the spiritual blessing on the people and their offsprings residing in the said territory. Such references in the holy book of the Jews are enough to convince them that their future is tied to the land between the Jordan River and the Mediterranean and that they should follow the Divine dictum in securing their borders and their people from other outside influences. The mention of water and filling up of the streams and the dry grounds are sufficient causes to garner control over the water resources vis-avis the Palestinians and without any sort of guilt or fear. On the other hand, Palestine is an important religious site in Islam for it consists of the famous Al-Aqsa mosque whose references are there in the Islamic Holy Book of the Koran (“Why Al-Aqsa mosque is important in the Israel-Palestine Conflict”, 2023). All of Islam’s earlier prophets have had resided in the Holy place of Palestine. Even it is believed that Prophet Muhammad travelled to the Al-Aqsa mosque one night from where He ascended to heaven thereby making Jerusalem and Al-Aqsa one of the most sensitive and holiest places in Islam after Mecca and Medina. In the Shahi Bhukari book of Islam it is mentioned that “not to withhold superfluous water for that will prevent people from grazing their cattle” (Bhukari, 1996, as cited in Khan, 2009, pg-533). There is even the reference that on the Day of Resurrection, Allah will not forgive people who had deliberately withheld superfluous water from travelers as well as the cattle. Going by the religious explanations, the Arabs in Palestine therefore have enough cause to consider the Jews as illegal immigrants and wicked people snatching away water for their day-to-day existence. Therefore hydrohegemony of Israel over Palestine and the subsequent religious overtones of the Palestinians give the conflict a sustained picture to the outside world.

Thirdly, Israel’s hydrohegemony was exacerbated by the availability of cheap rates of land along the Jordan River basins and in the central water dominant areas of the West Bank, especially in the famous Area-C along the central and eastern aquifers (Black, 2013,). The already affluent Jews

settled in that area mainly to promote agricultural development by boosting harvest and also fostering the industrial development of the Jewish state of Israel. Agriculture and industry- the two pillars of an economy are enough to articulate the vision of a national sentiment and float the concept of a separate and strong nationhood based on a developed and matured economy. In contrast to it, the Palestinians as the former inhabitants of the area were involved from a much earlier time period in primarily agricultural and pastoral activities. They refused to acquiesce to the Jewish superiority and the domineering attitude which was meted out against them in what they believe as their own land. They subsequently disagreed to dislocate from their own territory and became targets of Israeli attacks and threats. Thus continues the Israel-Palestine conflict and it assumes a perpetual hue given the deep-rooted sources of such rivalries.

In the ongoing Israel-Palestine conflict, the Hamas (the militant organization in Palestine and also the political group exercising control over both the Palestinian territories in the West Bank and the Gaza strip) forged deadly attacks on Israel due to the latter's continuous strikes on the already dwindling Palestinian land and economy. In response to the Hamas attacks, Israel's strategy purely hinted at the weaponization of water as the ploy of the last resort in order to wipe out the existence of Hamas from the Palestinian controlled West Bank and the Gaza strip (Houdret and Dombrowsky, 2024). Israel had devised a tripartite model to diffuse the Hamas from deploying any stronger military tactic to destroy Israel. Using water as a weapon, it has deliberately caused flooding, contamination and made access to fresh water sources almost elusive for them. In the Gaza strip in order to dissipate the Hamas underground guerilla tactics, the Israeli Defence Forces had vehemently pumped sea water into the tunnels which had a debilitating impact on the buildings, roads and other significant mansions in the Palestinian territory (Houdret and Dombrowsky, 2024). Also, the Israeli army had completely cut off all the possible channels of fresh water to the Hamas controlled Gaza strip. On top of that, the Israeli forces had destroyed all the major water and wastewater treatment plants. This had stopped the treatment of sewage and the groundwater got contaminated by unhealthy and fatal ingredients detrimental to human health. Israel in the wage of attacking the Palestinians had dropped the harmful white phosphorous which mixed with human feces

and seeped underground thereby poisoning the water in the Gaza strip, mainly that of the Coastal Aquifers- the only available spot of freshwater reserves. Due to the absence of standard levels of freshwater, the Palestinian population is compelled to fall at the mercy of the existing contaminated and fatal water to survive and remain alive. This inturn has decimated thousands of them and loosened the unity and valor to fight the Israelis back to their stations. By obstructing the flow of freshwater and by cutting all the pipelines, Israel showed hydrohegemony over the Palestinians in such a way that even if the Hamas or any ordinary Palestine citizen survived the Israeli attacks by a twist of fate, then also their survival chances would ultimately falter. Water has been tacitly used as a disastrous weapon to unleash a scathing attack on the Palestinian people without direct bloodshed. This would on one hand save the Israeli side from losing their best military minds and on the other hand reel the Palestinians in a quagmire of death. Currently the heavy Israeli bombardments besides creating irreconcilable damage and destruction to the people at the Gaza strip has also pushed them to the farthest and last edge of the territory- in a city called Rafah in southernmost Gaza. Water crisis in Rafah has reached an even more ghastly stage. The Palestinians have clung on to Rafah beyond which they do not have any safe haven to take shelter in (“All eyes on Rafah”, 2024). Either they escape to the Egyptian territory and again lead lives as refugees in miserable conditions or they are coerced to swallow poisonous water and be ready to die. Although illegal and inhuman in the eyes of the world, but to Israel their water weaponization and hydrohegemony has emerged as a plausible military tactic to disrupt and eradicate the very last signs of Palestinian vestiges from their Promised Land. The crammed Palestinians in Rafah have been forced to lead lives in squalid and dingy tents devoid of any food or proper sanitation facilities, be thirsty for weeks at a stretch and squirm under inhospitable and unhygienic conditions due to the lack of proper medical facilities. In the name of ‘limited operation’ against the Hamas whom Israel believes to have taken recourse in the southern most part of Gaza, Israel has simultaneously massacred the Palestinians using its water tactics- an act which catered to dual ends of Israel- destroying Hamas and Palestine and gaining strategic access to all water reserves in the territory.

Regional Repurcussions of Israel's Hydrohegemony and Water Weaponization

If Israel's hydrohegemony appears to be a game changer in hawkish foreign policy tactics, then it has followed the footsteps of its regional predecessors. Or it can be said that Israel's ongoing water threat can lead to a security dilemma among other parched nations across the region and this might stir a mad scramble for resource control. During the Syrian civil war, the ISIS (Islamic State of Iraq and Syria) had systematically used water as a weapon to intimidate the Iraqi forces. The ISIS in order to gain political control over Syria took charge of the key water reserves in the area. In its fight over a Shiite Iraq, the ISIS followed the strategies of flooding, contamination and cutting off the water pipelines in areas downstream of Iraq. The most noteworthy of such an incident is the control of the Fallujah Dam in the year 2014 by ISIS (Lossow, 2020,). The ISIS had withheld water from the Euphrates River and reduced the flow to the areas downstream in Baghdad. This led to agricultural difficulties in southern and central Iraq and poverty and hunger maligned the region. Many from those areas were abducted into the ISIS ideology in the absence of a steady income thereby expanding the ISIS's Islamic empire. The ISIS had also released the floodgates of the Dam later so that parts of Iraq could go submerged under water and undergo huge scale destruction. Over 60,000 people had lost their lives and more than 10,000 livestock, harvest and residents were swept away (Lossow, 2020,) Though the ISIS was defeated by the Coalition of states under the US leadership in 2019, reports from the US Department of State points out at a looming and diffused ISIS threat in the Sahel region (North and Central Africa between the Sahara and the Savanna). It hints at a possible resurgence of the ISIS across the region as various reports of attacks on water establishments have come to the forefront during the past years ("Al Qaeda claims responsibility for June attacks in Burkina Faso", 2024). The smaller wing of the ISIS and an Al-Qaeda affiliate had attacked soldiers in Burkina Faso while they were guarding critical water infrastructures ("Al Qaeda claims responsibility for June attacks in Burkina Faso", 2024). This marks the beginning of a renewed belligerency as these terrorist outfits can easily spread to their original strongholds and continue to operate with a more unified strategy. Israel's hydrohegemony can newly inspire the remnants of such deadly outfits to resurface and function in a much broader territorial span. The possibility

of such a conflict will further bring in new power equations among major powers who have always vied for influence in the West Asian matrix for resource diplomacy. This is bound to unleash fresh wave of geopolitical rivalries and augment tensions in West Asia. Hydrohegemony and water politics can kick start the already hostile equations among Iran-backed Hamas, the ISIS, Iraq, Yemen, and Saudi Arabia and so on. The Jewish Palestine affront can swiftly turn into a Shia-Sunni ambush engulfing the whole of West Asia.

Another example of such regional repercussions is the already ongoing conflict in Yemen. Yemen, a water scarce country has faced more severe water crisis due to the same water weaponization tactics used by the Houthi rebels on the Yemeni government. The Houthis have cut off all the essential routes of water supplies in the Taizz city controlled and governed by the Yemeni government (“Yemen: warring parties deepen water crisis” , 2023). From an interstate perspective, the Saudis have also launched attacks on the Houthis whom they thought to be working with Iran and in the process they too have brought about monumental damage to the water infrastructure of Yemen. Though Saudi Arabia has stopped the intractable conflict with the Houthis and moved forward with its national development since 2019, the Houthi attacks on the ships of Saudi led coalition countries including USA, UK and other Gulf nations has raised eyebrows once more. The Houthis are striking these nations out of their solidarity with Palestine and against Israel’s hydrohegemonic policies. Though it can be seen that tension between the Houthis and the Saudis have reduced to a significant degree in the past years, but no peace deal has been guaranteed by them. The disastrous attacks on the Saudi Aramco in 2019 are itself a warning to the lethality of the attacks that can be inflicted by the Houthis. For now, the tense situation between the Houthis and the Saudis have ebbed but in recent times the Houthis have openly threatened Israel to restrain its activities in the Gaza strip or it would put a mounting pressure on the ships of the western nations travelling through the Red Sea carrying oil. The US plan of expanding the Abraham Accords and bringing about the normalization of Saudi-Israel ties will spark hostility from the Houthis and exacerbate the situation further. The Saudis so far have not shown any warm reception towards the Abraham Accords but forging deals with the western nations especially the US (a close ally of Israel) will contain the seeds of further angst across West Asia. Also, Israel’s

hydrohegemony can backfire peace across the whole of West Asia. Countries in West Asia and North Africa who are part of the Abraham Accords like UAE, Bahrain and Morocco may become victims of deadly attacks by the Houthis in relation to Israel's deadly strikes against Palestinians. Therefore, the long standing effects of hydrohegemony and water weaponization by Israel has the spillover effects of a regional repercussion in a contested, water-deficient and conflict ridden West Asia. This can escalate into a protracted and full blown war with major powers taking either sides and consolidating their power equations in the oil rich zone. Israel's water politics can upturn the power dynamics in West Asia and may bring a domino effect to other water deficient nations fighting with some rival terrorist outfits for political influence.

Conclusion

The significance of resources in war is stemmed from the traditional political and economic vulnerabilities of resource dependent nations. Israel and Palestine- two states with contested political boundaries and crippled economic prowess are equally dependent on water which is a crucial resource for survival. It is in this context that Israel, a more realistic and cautious party has tried to grab control over all water resources and weaponize it to gain legitimacy and preponderance vis-à-vis Palestine. The geopolitics over water among Israel and Palestine has the potential to turn into a disaster anytime soon, with the ultimate outcome being utter destruction and massacre of millions of innocent civilians. The resource allocation among nations has always been political and diplomatic and even if a temporary thaw emerges out of third party interventions, national security and interest can bypass peace talks among them. In the current scenario, West Asia presents a complex mesh of coalitions and counter coalitions where resource weaponization seems the only path to yield and stick to power over a considerable period of time. But again, in the name of resource scarcity and resource mobilization, no state has the right to inflict insurmountable hardships on humanity. If hydrohegemony is the decided policy stance of Israel for the next few years over Palestine, then the world needs to intervene to save the Palestinians. The international community leaving aside their political gains and diplomatic breakthroughs should adopt the Responsibility to Protect (R2P) principle in accordance with the UN Charter in order to prevent such vile acts against humanity. Cutting off water supplies and

using water as a weapon to kill human beings possess the cruelest form of violence against humanity. If not contained, this single strategy can have the diabolical impact of nuclear weapons across West Asia. Though the intensity of the nuclear weapons is swifter, the intensity and impact of water weaponization is a slow poison meant to end lives today or tomorrow. If water which ensures the very basis of survival of all life in the planet is turned into a poison or is removed for human consumption, then it will surely end up the existence of life on the earth. Such acts of hydrohegemony and water weaponization must be eradicated by legal ways like signing treaties and pacts on a global scale to stop using crucial resources as weapons of war. This will obviously require time but the awareness should be instilled among nations across the globe. Water weaponization must gain the same weight as other pressing global issues like climate change, poverty, hunger, terrorism and gender disparities. If it assumes such a global outlook, then acts of such insanity can be lowered. If the future is marked by intense water wars, then the central point of Israel-Palestine conflict ie fighting for the land will lose its meaning. Future water wars will compel nations towards mutual destruction and a gradual end. Much like the concept of deterrence in case of the nuclear weapons, the international community must single out the attacking nation and curb water facilities to it thereby bringing a halt to such atrocities. In today's world besides the lethality of the nuclear weapons, they are paradoxically also termed as weapons of peace. On a similar note, peace for water can be a new adage in the current century to deter the disastrous effects of such a scenario. Therefore the water centric saga of Israel-Palestine conflict must not be entertained for petty political interests in a fragile and water deficient West Asia.

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